

Heterogeneous computing for Deep Learning: deploying generative models via Intel OneAPI

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

This project is intended to test Intel oneAPI as a framework to speedup DL training processes across multiple HW architectures using Intel® AI Analytics Toolkit. A Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) is used to make the tests which are run on a Intel(R) Xeon(R) Platinum 8260 (codenamed "Cascade Lake") node.

ABSTRACT

The main goal of the project is to test Intel's oneAPI as a framework to speed up the 3DGAN training processes across multiple hardware architectures. The work consists in analyzing the behavior of 3DGAN under Intel oneAPI by using the Intel AI Analytics Toolkit. This toolkit provides Python frameworks and tools to accelerate end-to-end data science and analytics pipelines on Intel architectures. It uses oneAPI libraries for low-level compute optimizations, thus, maximizing performance from preprocessing through machine learning. As a result, oneAPI made a difference, the model converged faster.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION	05
<hr/>	
INTEL ONEAPI	05
<hr/>	
INTEL® AI ANALYTICS TOOLKIT	
<hr/>	
3DGAN	06
<hr/>	
SETUP	07
<hr/>	
EXPERIMENTS	
BETA 8	
BETA 9	08
<hr/>	
RESULTS	09
<hr/>	
INTEL - CERN SOCIAL MEDIA	12
<hr/>	
CONCLUSION	12
<hr/>	
BIBLIOGRAPHY	13

1. INTRODUCTION

Deep Learning applications are multiplying in all fields of science and society. Performance of those models is strictly related to the availability of compute intensive hardware and methods to deploy the AI software that can ease the development, optimization and training processes. At CERN, the overwhelming majority of its current computing infrastructure is made of CPUs, this is critical for machine learning since there are other architectures that are more suitable for this kind of problem. Moreover, High Energy Physics software requires high parallelization and multithreading making the community look for ways to modernize the code for future different hardware architectures.

In consequence, an heterogeneous computing approach seems to be the trend, as far as Deep Learning is concerned, and industry is investing in dedicated hardware that promises to deliver impressive performance in terms of inference and training. In this respect a unified software development environment across CPU and accelerator architectures could highly simplify models development. Intel oneAPI could be one of these ways.

Intel oneAPI toolkits, and in particular Intel oneAPI DL Framework Developer Toolkit, aim at delivering a set of high performance tools for building applications for Intel Xeon Scalable processors and Intel Accelerators. This project will be using Intel® AI Analytics Toolkit to test Intel oneAPIs usage and results using a GAN model, called 3DGAN, developed by CERN openlab, aimed at simulating the HEP detector's response.

2. INTEL ONEAPI

Intel oneAPI provides libraries and a unified language that offer full native code performance across a range of hardware, including CPUs, GPUs, FPGAs and AI accelerators.

a. Intel® AI Analytics Toolkit

The Intel® AI Analytics Toolkit is one of the toolkits provided by oneAPI that gives data scientists, AI developers, and researchers Python* tools and frameworks to accelerate end-to-end data science and analytics pipelines on Intel® architectures. The components are built using oneAPI libraries for low-level compute optimizations. This maximizes performance from pre-processing through machine learning.

With this toolkit it is possible to [1]:

- Deliver high-performance deep learning (DL) training on Intel® XPUs and integrate fast inference into AI development workflows with Intel-optimized DL frameworks: TensorFlow* and PyTorch*, pretrained models, and low-precision tools.
- Achieve drop-in acceleration for data analytics and machine learning workflows with compute-intensive Python* packages: Modin*, NumPy, Numba, scikit-learn*, and XGBoost* optimized for Intel.
- Gain direct access to Intel analytics and AI optimizations to ensure that different software libraries work together seamlessly.

Figure 1 shows what is inside the Intel® AI Analytics Toolkit.

1. *What's inside Intel® AI Analytics Toolkit.*

3. 3DGAN

CERN's Large Hadron Collider (LHC) is currently using Monte Carlo (MC) techniques in order to simulate the calorimeters energy response. However, the MC simulation is resource intensive and time consuming. The future High-Luminosity Large Hadron Collider (HL-LHC) will require faster methods. To accomplish that, studies are on-going to understand how the Monte Carlo simulation can be replaced by Deep Learning algorithms trained to generate detectors output interpreted as 3-dimensional images. In this case, the DL algorithm is a 3D convolutional Generative Adversarial Network (3DGAN), developed by CERN openlab: it achieves a speed up of more than three orders of magnitude as compared to the MC simulation. Figure 2 shows the 3DGAN architecture [2].

2. *3DGANs Architecture.*

The second goal of this project is to improve the training process of the 3DGAN model. The shorter the training time the easiest it will be to generalize GAN models to different detector geometries and here is where oneAPI could help. Even though oneAPI does not aim at accelerating the training process, but to be compatible with different architectures, a difference in the training time should be noticed since oneAPI tries to get the best out of the available hardware.

4. SETUP

In order to simplify the study, a benchmark based on 2D convolutions instead of 3D convolutions was developed. The code can be found at: <https://github.com/svalleco/3Dgan/tree/svalleco/2Dtest>. We use Python3.7.

To get to work with oneAPI, the following steps were done:

1. We called with 'source .../setvars.sh' the oneAPI environment. (oneAPI and Intel® AI Analytics Toolkit were already installed) See Figure 3.

```
[sdonayre@p1csl-02 ~]$ source /cvmfs/projects.cern.ch/intelsw/oneAPI/linux/x86_64/2021/beta8/setvars.sh
:: initializing oneAPI environment ...
:: ccl -- latest
:: ipp -- latest
:: mkl -- latest
:: mpi -- latest
:: tbb -- latest
:: vpl -- latest
:: cclx -- latest
:: daal -- latest
:: dnnl -- latest
:: itac -- latest
:: ippcp -- latest
:: vtune -- latest
:: advisor -- latest
:: compiler -- latest
:: debugger -- latest
:: dpcpp-ct -- latest
:: inspector -- latest
:: intelpython -- latest
:: dev-utilities -- latest
:: IQT -- latest
:: pytorch -- latest
:: modelzoo -- latest
:: tensorflow -- latest
:: oneAPI environment initialized ::
```

3.

Initializing oneAPI environment.

2. We selected the desired conda environment, among those provided by the toolkit. See Figure 4.

```
/afs/cern.ch/work/s/sdonayre/silke_base
/afs/cern.ch/work/s/sdonayre/silke_inteltensorflow
base * /cvmfs/projects.cern.ch/intelsw/oneAPI/linux/x86_64/2021/beta8/intelpython/latest
pytorch /cvmfs/projects.cern.ch/intelsw/oneAPI/linux/x86_64/2021/beta8/intelpython/latest/envs/pytorch
pytorch-1.5.0 /cvmfs/projects.cern.ch/intelsw/oneAPI/linux/x86_64/2021/beta8/intelpython/latest/envs/pytorch-1.5.0
tensorflow /cvmfs/projects.cern.ch/intelsw/oneAPI/linux/x86_64/2021/beta8/intelpython/latest/envs/tensorflow
tensorflow-2.1.0 /cvmfs/projects.cern.ch/intelsw/oneAPI/linux/x86_64/2021/beta8/intelpython/latest/envs/tensorflow-2.1.0
```

4.

Conda environments provided by the toolkit.

3. We optimised level of parallelism of the GAN training process by adjusting Tensorflow `inter_op_parallelism_threads` (Set number of threads used for parallelism between independent operations.) and `intra_op_parallelism_threads` (Set number of threads used within an individual op for parallelism.) parameters. This numbers depend on the number of cores and sockets available. See Figure 5.


```
'''
Environment settings:
Set MKLDNN_VERBOSE=1 to show DNNL run time verbose
Set KMP_AFFINITY=verbose to show OpenMP thread information
'''

config = tf.ConfigProto(inter_op_parallelism_threads = 1, intra_op_parallelism_threads = 96)
#log_device_placement=True
session = tf.Session(config=config)
K.set_session(session)

#import os; os.environ["MKLDNN_VERBOSE"] = "1"
#import os; os.environ["MKL_VERBOSE"] = "1"
import os; os.environ["KMP_AFFINITY"] = "granularity=tile,compact"#,1,0"
os.environ["KMP_BLOCKTIME"] = "0"
os.environ["KMP_SETTINGS"] = "1"
```

5. *Tensorflow parameters settings.*

After having this configuration, we proceed testing oneApi with different Tensorflow versions.

5. EXPERIMENTS

We tested the Intel® AI Analytics Toolkit using TF 1.15 (Version BETA 8), TF 2.1 (BETA 8) and TF 2.2 (BETA 9). BETA X are different Intel® AI Analytics Toolkit versions. The original source code was written to run only with TF 1.15. In order to run the same code but with TF 2.1 and TF 2.2, some modifications were made. The files can be found at: <https://github.com/svalleco/3Dgan/tree/silkedh/KerasTF2>.

a. BETA 8

For this experiment we activated the conda 'base' environment with the command:

```
'conda activate tensorflow'
```

Then, we proceeded installing the missing packages that were **keras 2.4**, **threadpoolctl 2.1.0** and **intel-tensorflow 1.15**.

We ran the code and verified that Intel MKL-DNN and Intel DL Boost were correctly enabled. The output is visible in Figure 6.

```
Epoch 1 of 30
0.4466 [.....] - ETA: 0s(128, 1, 25, 25)
(128, 1)
mkldnn_verbose,info,Intel MKL-DNN v0.20.3 (commit N/A)
mkldnn_verbose,info,Detected ISA is Intel AVX-512 with Intel DL Boost
mkldnn_verbose,exec,reorder,simple:any,undef,in:f32_nchw out:f32_nchw16c,num:1,32x8x7x8,0.0581055
mkldnn_verbose,exec,reorder,simple:any,undef,in:f32_hw16 out:f32_O1hw16i16o,num:1,64x8x6x8,0.0838078
mkldnn_verbose,exec,convolution,jit:avx512_common,forward_training,fsrc:nChw16c fwei:0Ihw16i16o fbia:undef fdst:nChw16c,alg:convolution_direct,mb32_ic8oc64_ih7oh7kh6sh1dh0ph2_lw8ow8kw8sw1dw0pw3,0.362061
mkldnn_verbose,exec,eltwise,jit:avx512_common,forward_training,fdats:blocked fdiff:undef,alg:eltwise_relu,mb32ic64ih7iw8,0.045166
mkldnn_verbose,exec,reorder,jit:uni,undef,in:f32_blocked out:f32_blocked,num:1,32x64x7x8,0.0891113
mkldnn_verbose,exec,reorder,jit:uni,undef,in:f32_blocked out:f32_blocked,num:1,32x14x16x64,0.140889
mkldnn_verbose,exec,reorder,jit:uni,undef,in:f32_nchw out:f32_nchw16c,num:1,32x64x18x16,0.741943
mkldnn_verbose,exec,convolution,jit:avx512_common,forward_training,fsrc:nChw16c fwei:0Ihw16i16o fbia:undef fdst:nChw16c,alg:convolution_direct,mb32_ic64oc6_ih18oh14kh5sh1dh0ph0_iw16ow9kw8sw1dw0pw0,0.422119
mkldnn_verbose,exec,reorder,simple:any,undef,in:f32_nchw16c out:f32_nchw,num:1,32x6x14x9,0.0290527
mkldnn_verbose,exec,eltwise,jit:avx512_common,forward_training,fdats:blocked fdiff:undef,alg:eltwise_relu,mb32ic64ih14iw9,0.0180664
mkldnn_verbose,exec,reorder,jit:uni,undef,in:f32_blocked out:f32_blocked,num:1,32x6x14x9,0.0220492
mkldnn_verbose,exec,reorder,jit:uni,undef,in:f32_blocked out:f32_blocked,num:1,32x28x27x6,0.162109
mkldnn_verbose,exec,reorder,simple:any,undef,in:f32_nchw out:f32_nchw16c,num:1,32x6x28x33,0.0581055
mkldnn_verbose,exec,reorder,simple:any,undef,in:f32_hw16 out:f32_O1hw16i16o,num:1,64x8x8x8,0.0141602
mkldnn_verbose,exec,convolution,jit:avx512_common,forward_training,fsrc:nChw16c fwei:0Ihw16i16o fbia:undef fdst:nChw16c,alg:convolution_direct,mb32_ic6oc6_ih28oh26kh3sh1dh0ph0_iw33ow26kw8sw1dw0pw0,0.375
mkldnn_verbose,exec,reorder,simple:any,undef,in:f32_nchw16c out:f32_nchw,num:1,32x6x26x26,0.0349121
mkldnn_verbose,exec,eltwise,jit:avx512_common,forward_training,fdats:blocked fdiff:undef,alg:eltwise_relu,mb32ic64ih26iw26,0.0568848
mkldnn_verbose,exec,reorder,simple:any,undef,in:f32_nchw out:f32_nchw16c,num:1,32x6x26x26,0.0410156
mkldnn_verbose,exec,convolution,jit:avx512_common,forward_training,fsrc:nChw16c fwei:0Ihw16i16o fbia:undef fdst:nChw16c,alg:convolution_direct,mb32_ic6oc1_ih26oh25kh2sh1dh0ph0_iw26ow25kw2sw1dw0pw0,0.06982
mkldnn_verbose,exec,convolution,jit:avx512_common,forward_training,fsrc:nChw16c fwei:0Ihw16i16o fbia:undef fdst:nChw16c,alg:convolution_direct,mb32_ic6oc1_ih26oh25kh2sh1dh0ph0_iw26ow25kw2sw1dw0pw0,0.06982
```

6. *Usage of oneAPI - Programm output.*

8. *Loss comparison using intra and inter parameters.*

We compared the performance obtained by taking the best configuration for each case and got the following output, see Figure 9:

9. *Generation and Auxiliary loss the best configuration for each case.*

We can see that oneAPIs behaviour, on CPUs, is very close to the one achieved with the GPU. It converges faster than the model trained without oneAPI.

In addition, we validated that the physics output provided by the model calculating a set of physics quantities that can be used to model the detector response. An example is shown in figure 10: the two panel compare the ratio of the calculated energy and the real energy deposited in the cells for Monte Carlo (in red) and GAN generated data (in blue). The oneAPI run is shown on the right.

10. Energy ratio with and without oneAPI.

We can see that there are some differences between the graphs. The one that most resembles the expected output is the one obtained using oneAPI. For the generation of both graphs, the default parameter was set for the training of the model without oneAPI and the intra and inter parameters for the model trained with oneAPI, so we could get the best achievable performance on both.

We also measured the training time, see Figure 11.

11. Training time with oneAPI and without oneAPI.

The image above shows us that, overall training time per epoch becomes larger using oneAPI, however losses seem to converge faster.

Additional work is needed to optimise training to convergence and explore additional Tensorflow configurations.

7. INTEL - CERN VODCAST

For the completion of the project a social media post and a Vodcast were made in collaboration with Intel. The first post was posted on October (see Figure 12) to introduce people to Intel oneAPI. The second post will be released on January 2021 together with the Vodcast.

12. *Training time with oneAPI and without oneAPI.*

For the Vodcast a kit was sent by Caffeli, a company that was working with Intel in order to make the social media posts. The kit came with a camera, microphone and lightning to make the video as professional as possible. Figure 13 shows the Vodcast kit.

8. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Intel oneAPI may be a really good alternative for a unified software development environment. The experiments showed us that with the correct setting of parameters, we can get a faster convergence when training the model. Moreover, the same code can be used on an Intel GPU without any changes. Overall, my experience during this project was really nice, I participated to weekly meetings to see what the group was working on and learned about quantum computing. It was very exciting!

The interview experience was also one of a kind, I had never done something like that before. I also met very kind people that helped me with the organization and guidance of the project. Thanks a lot to Sofia Vallecorsa for teaching me more about GANs and being always available for questions and to CERN openlab for providing me this opportunity.

13.

TCafelli's Vodcast kit.

The interview (vodcast) was given by Robert Duffy, a well-known american politician. The interview lasted 15 minutes and it was via Zoom.

9. BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] Intel, Intel oneAPI, 2020. <https://software.intel.com/content/www/us/en/develop/tools/oneapi/ai-analytics-toolkit.html>
- [2] Khattak, Gul rukh et al. High Energy Physics Detector Simulation using Generative Adversarial Networks with Domain Related Constraints. 2020.